

LOCAL STRAIN FIELDS IN PARTICULATE METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES CHARACTERIZED BY THE OBJECT GRATING TECHNIQUE

Y. L. Liu¹ and G. Fischer²

¹ *Materials Department, Risø National Laboratory,
Frederiksborgvej 399, P.O. Box 49, DK-4000 Roskilde, Denmark*

² *Quality Assurance Department, Dortmund University,
D-44227 Dortmund, Germany*

SUMMARY: This paper addresses the experimental characterization of local strain distribution in Al6061-10% Al₂O₃ and Al6061-20% Al₂O₃ particulate composites under deformation using the object grating technique. The maximum overall strain of the specimen deformed by bending or tension in SEM is 2-3%. The lateral resolution and strain measurement accuracy of this technique allow the local strain field associated with large particles to be characterized. Strain maps of particles of different geometries have been obtained and the effects of particle geometry on the constrained plastic flow in the matrix are analyzed and compared to FEM predictions.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composite, object grating technique, deformation, local strain distribution, constrained plastic flow.

INTRODUCTION

The presence of the hard, plastically undeformable reinforcement in the ductile matrix changes radically the stress/strain fields in the vicinity of the reinforcement when a metal matrix composite (MMC) is strained. The characteristics of the stress/strain field are affected by geometry and distribution of the reinforcement. The study of the evolution of the local stress/strain fields is essential for improved understanding of the overall elastic and plastic response, and of the strengthening mechanisms of the composite. Numerical techniques such as FEM (Finite Element Model) have been widely used in recent years, where the phase geometry, thermomechanical properties of phases and non-uniform local stress and strain fields are easily accounted for in the simulation of overall mechanical response [1-3]. These models have been used successfully to make quantitative predictions about the overall stress-strain behaviour of such materials. On the local scale they demonstrate that the hydrostatic stresses lead to constrained plastic deformation. The degree of constraint is dependent on the geometrical shape and arrangement of reinforcement.

Various experimental techniques have been developed to characterize the local distribution of stress/strain in MMCs for comparison with FEM simulations. High energy synchrotron radiation [4] has been used to determine the local stress field in bulk material of a composite by measuring the lattice (elastic) strain of small volumes deep within the material. This technique provides the possibility of in-situ measurements, but the lateral resolution is low

(tens and hundreds of microns). TEM (Transmission Electron Microscopy) and EBSD (Electron BackScattered Pattern) have been used to determine the local dislocation density as a measure of the local plastic strain [5,6]. These methods have high lateral resolution in the order of microns or less. But the strain measure is indirect.

Object grating methods [7] have been used to characterize the strain fields on the bulk specimen surface of inhomogeneous materials in the past decades. To meet the new challenge of applying this technique to local strain investigation in particulate reinforced MMCs where both high lateral resolution and high accuracy of strain measurement are required, a more sophisticated object grating method has been developed [8,9]. This method combined with a stress-rig in a scanning electron microscope (SEM) allows the local strain distribution to be studied in-situ during deformation. The experimental procedure consists of: 1) the deposition of a grating on the polished specimen surface by photolithography, 2) deforming the specimen in a SEM by bending or tension, taking digital images at different stages of deformation, 3) image processing, and 4) computation of strain components. Finally the measured strains are plotted in 2D-strain maps.

With the aim to evaluate numerical predictions of the local behaviour, the MMC materials of Al6061 containing 10 or 20% Al₂O₃ particulates are investigated using this object grating technique. The maximum overall strain reached by bending or tension is 2-3%. In this paper, the characteristic strain field in the vicinity of the reinforcement particles revealed by this technique is described, the effects of particle geometry are analyzed and compared to FEM predictions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The materials Al6061-10% Al₂O₃ and Al6061-20% Al₂O₃ are supplied by Duralcan, USA. The as-received materials are in the form of extrusion rod. The measured mean particle size of Al₂O₃ is 6 - 8 μm, while the particle size distribution ranges from <5 μm to about 30 μm. Bending and tensile specimens (Fig.1) are machined from the extruded rods in such a way that the longitudinal axis of the specimen is parallel to the original extrusion direction.

Fig. 1: Bending (a) and tensile (b) specimens.

The grating distance has to be chosen so that it remains sufficiently small in comparison to the smallest wavelength of the expected strain field. In this work grating distance of 1.5 μm is applied. The deposition of gold grating dots is described elsewhere [9].

The specimen is strained in a stress-rig (Raith GmbH, Dortmund) inside a JEOL 840 SEM. The loading is applied by the crosshead displacement at a constant speed of 50 mm/min, corresponding to a strain rate of 10^{-5} - 10^{-4} s $^{-1}$ in the case of tensile tests. A typical stress-strain curve recorded during tension is given in Fig. 2. For tensile tests the overall strain is recorded by an extensometer. The test is interrupted at various strains. Without unloading, digitized images of the area of interest are taken at each deformation step. Also digitized images before loading (as a reference image), and after final unloading are recorded.

Fig. 2: Stress-strain curve recorded during tensile testing in SEM. 1-8 indicate the deformation steps where the load is held and the image is taken.

Fig. 3: Schematic drawing showing subimage, centre and overlapping of subimages.

The especially developed algorithm for image processing [8,9] divides the whole image into many subimages (Fig. 3). The algorithm is iteratively searching the best local and grey value transformation of each subimage in the deformed state to the corresponding subimage in the undeformed state. As a result, an average set of local transformation parameters for each subimage is calculated. The in-plane strain components ϵ_{xx} , ϵ_{yy} and ϵ_{xy} at the centre point of each subimage can be derived on the basis of these transformation parameters. The equivalent strain ϵ_{equ} is calculated as

$$\epsilon_{equ} = 2/3 (\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2) \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are principal strains. The mathematics for image processing and strain component calculations are given elsewhere [8,9]. Finally contours of strain ϵ_{equ} are plotted on the top of the deformed image to visualize the distribution of strain over the microstructural inhomogeneities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Strain Measure Accuracy and Lateral Resolution

All the strain measurements are performed on the surface of the specimen. One has to assume that there is no free-surface effect, so the obtained surface information has also a three-dimensional significance. The previous work [9] shows that the measured strain value while the load is held is a sum of elastic and plastic strains. Since the elastic strain value is very low and remains constant in the elastic-plastic region, the measured strain can be considered to represent the evolution of the plastic strain.

The algorithm determines the displacement of the subimage centre with subpixel accuracy (0.2 - 0.3 pixel) (see Fig. 3). With a subimage size of 64 pixel, accuracy for strain measure is therefore estimated to be in the range of 0.3 to 0.5 % [9]. The improvement in strain accuracy compared with that of the algorithm used by other authors [7] is significant. The latter [7] extracts the individual dots and gives an accuracy of about 1 pixel to determine the displacement of the centre of each dot.

The lateral resolution is improved with decreasing grating distance and subimage size [9]. The presently used grating distance of 1.5 μm is practically the smallest grating distance which can be made on the surface of this type of material by means of photolithography. For statistical reasons a least number of grey level edges within a subimage is needed to secure the measuring accuracy. The selection of the subimage size is therefore a compromise between lateral resolution (a small subimage is wanted) and strain accuracy (a large subimage is preferred). In the present work, a combination of the grating distance of 1.5 μm and the subimage size of 64x64 pixel (2.5x2.5 μm) is used. Generally the local strain field around particles greater than 10 - 15 μm can be characterized [9].

Characterization of Local Strain Fields

With the aim of making a comparison with FEM simulations which are based on ideal arrays of reinforcement, the particles of interest in the experiment are selected as follows: they are close to a regular shape and reasonably isolated.

Al6061-20%Al₂O₃

The first set of experiments is carried out using bending specimens of Al6061-20%Al₂O₃. Due to the high volume concentration of the Al₂O₃ particles and the small particle spacing (calculated value 13 μm), it is very difficult, if not impossible, to find an isolated particle. Typical microstructure is shown in Fig. 4 where a large particle (about 20 x 30 μm) is surrounded by many small particles at rather small particle spacing. The shape of the large particle is irregular and it is not aligned with the loading direction. A series of strain maps of this area at different deformation steps has been obtained, of which two examples are shown in Fig. 4 (a) and (b). The overall strain of these two deformation steps is 1.7 and 3.3%, respectively. (The overall strain is taken as the mean ϵ_{equ} value over the whole image area).

Fig. 4: Strain maps of Al6061-20%Al₂O₃ specimen deformed by bending at overall strains of (a) 1.7% and (b) 3.3%..

The characteristic information about the strain field one can obtain from the strain maps in Fig. 4 is:

- 1) A systematic development of the strain field with the increasing overall strain can be visualized.
- 2) The strain in the Al₂O₃ particles is lower than 1% in the whole deformation process studied, apart from a few exceptions in which the strain line of 1% penetrates into the particles. This agrees with the fact that the Al₂O₃ particles are not plastically deformable.
- 3) The deformation introduces large strain gradients in the matrix region close to the reinforcement particles.
- 4) Strain localization has different origins. The occurrence of high strain localization in the matrix may be related to the sharp corner of particle or to a given particle distribution [1-3, 5]. However, the present microstructural examination shows that high strain peaks are often associated with micro-voids/cracks [9]. In the studied composites these micro-defects are possibly present in the initial state, and new micro-defects may develop at the early stage of deformation. It is therefore important to distinguish the strain localization caused by the particle geometry and by the presence of micro-voids/cracks. Examples of strain localization of the latter type can be seen in Fig. 4(b), such as the strain contour lines of i and h near the interface in the lower part of the figure. Similarly the high strain contour lines (> 1%) within the particle are often found to be associated with micro-cracks of the particle.

Al6061-10%Al₂O₃

Further experiments are carried out by uniaxial tension of Al6061-10%Al₂O₃ specimens. The lower concentration of particles and the larger particle spacing in this material (calculated

particle spacing $18\ \mu\text{m}$) give rise to more possibilities of finding reasonably isolated particles. Two particles of different geometries are selected: one has an aspect ratio of ~ 3 and is aligned to the direction of tensile loading (Fig. 5(a)), whereas the other has an aspect ratio of ~ 1.5 and the axis of the particle is 45° to the direction of loading (Fig. 5(b)). These two particles will be referred as A and B, respectively in the following text. One must bear in mind that these observations are made on the specimen surface, which is only a cross section of the material. On the basis of Fig. 5, we assume that the shapes of particle A and B are close to the ideal shapes of an aligned cylinder and a double-cone, respectively. The cross section of the two ideal shapes is shown schematically in Fig. 6.

Loading \updownarrow 20 μm

Symbol	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j	k
r_{max} [%]	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

a

Fig. 5: Strain maps of Al6061-10%Al₂O₃ specimen deformed by tension at an overall strain of 0.4%. (a) particle A, and (b) particle B.

Fig. 6: Cross section of the ideal shapes. (a) aligned cylinder, and (b) double-cone.

The images of the areas which include the selected particles are taken at overall tensile strains of 0.4, 1.1, 3.1 and 4.6%. Immediately after the stage 4 (4.6%) the specimen fractures. This paper will concentrate on the study of strain distribution at a very early stage of deformation (strain of 0.4%) shown in Fig. 5 (a) and (b). The contour line of 1% follows the particle/matrix interface quite well implying that the strain map is a good description of the strain field around the particle.

Further investigation reveals that for both particles intense matrix plastic deformation occurs along a direction of about 45° to the tensile axis. But the extent of plastic flow is different. Consider the contour line of 1% (c line) in the two maps in Fig. 5, the matrix portion with a strain greater than this value forms three continuous bands along the 45° direction (which is parallel to the interface) for particle B (Fig. 5(b)). The scale of these bands is about $30\ \mu\text{m}$ long and $5\ \mu\text{m}$ wide. But for the particle A (Fig. 5(a)), the matrix region with a strain greater than 1% is small and discontinuous in most cases, only one long band can be seen in the lower-right part of the particle. This indicates that for the aligned particle with a higher aspect ratio (particle A), the plastic flow path is to a larger extent interrupted as compared to particle B.

FEM analysis made by Shen et al. [2] can be correlated with the present observations. The shapes of particles studied in this FEM work, among others, are cylinder and double-cone (Fig. 6). At an average axial strain of 0.5% under tensile loading, the plastic deformation bands in the matrix at 45° to the tensile axis are continuous for the double-cone particle, whereas this pattern is interrupted for the cylinder, particularly for the aligned cylinder with an aspect ratio greater than 1 (whisker) (Fig. 6 in [2]). As the ideal shapes of the aligned cylinder and the double-cone are assumed to be related to the shapes of particles A and B, respectively, the comparison between the FEM predictions and the experimental observations shows good qualitative agreement. It is understood that such effects of particle shape on the local plastic flow pattern within the matrix are caused by the differences in the level of hydrostatic stress and the differences in constrained plastic flow in the matrix [2].

In Fig. 5. it can also be seen that strain tends to be more concentrated at the end of particle A, but distributed more uniformly around the particle B. This is in agreement with TEM observations [5] where it is reported that the ends of an aligned whisker (aspect ratio 5) are particularly associated with early dislocation generation, while the dislocation structure around a particle (smaller aspect ratio) is more homogeneous. According to FEM predictions [2], the highest strain localization associated with the end and the sharp corner of an aligned whisker is about two times of that associated with a double-cone particle. However, this “sharp corner” effect has not been observed in the present experiment. The direct explanation for the disagreement is that the shape of studied particles in the real composites is more smooth and without sharp corners, by comparison with the assumptions in FEM calculations. The observed highest strain localization for both particles shown in Fig 5 is, independent of shape, at the level of 4% (contour line f in Fig. 5(a) and (b)), which is about 10 times the overall strain. The occurrence of such high strain localization may be associated with the early void initiation (see above), the chance of which may well be similar for both particles. The strain localization caused by void formation is so intense that the effect of the “sharp corner” of the aligned particle, if there is any, is likely to be concealed.

CONCLUSIONS

The newly developed object grating technique is a powerful tool for characterizing local strain fields in metal matrix composites in-situ during deformation in a SEM. The strain distribution in the matrix around particles greater than $10 - 15\ \mu\text{m}$ can be characterized. The accuracy of strain measurement is in the range of 0.3 - 0.5%. The development of the strain field in a low strain range of 2-3% can be followed. Strain maps of particles of different geometries in particulate composites Al6061-10%Al₂O₃ and Al6061-20%Al₂O₃ have been obtained at early stages of deformation by bending/tension. The effects of particle geometry on the constrained plastic flow in the matrix have been visualized. For the aligned particle with an aspect ratio of

3, the strain in the matrix tends to be more concentrated at the end of the particle and the 45° plastic flow pattern is often interrupted, whereas the strain around the 45° aligned particle with an aspect ratio close to 1 is more homogeneous and continuous plastic deformation bands are formed. The comparison with FEM predictions shows good qualitative agreement. However, the disagreement suggests that the very high constraint effect at the end and corner of an aligned cylinder predicted by FEM is an overestimation of the situation in the real material.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the German Research Foundation (DFG) and by the Danish research program MP²M “Centre for Materials Processing, Properties and Modelling”.

REFERENCES

1. Sørensen, N.J., Hansen, N. and Liu, Y.L., “On the Inelastic Behaviour of Metal Matrix Composites”, *Proceedings 15th Risø International Symposium on Materials Science*, Andersen, S.I., Bilde-Sørensen, J.B., Lorentzen, T., Pedersen, O.B. and Sørensen, N.J., Eds., Risø National Laboratory, Roskilde, Denmark, 1994, pp. 149-168.
2. Shen, Y.-L., Finot, M., Needleman, A. and Suresh, S., “Effective Plastic Response of Two-Phase Composites”, *Acta Metall. Mater.*, Vol. 43, No. 4, 1995, pp. 1701-1722.
3. Watt, D.F., Xu, X.Q. and Lloyd, D.J., “Effects of Particle Morphology and Spacing on the Strain Fields in a Plastically Deforming Matrix”, *Acta Mater.*, Vol. 44, No. 2, 1996, pp. 789-799.
4. Poulsen, H.F., Lorentzen, T., Feidenhans'l, R. and Liu, Y.L., “A Synchrotron X-ray diffraction Study of the Local Residual Strains Around a Single Inclusion in an Al/W Metal-Matrix Composite”, *Metall. Trans.*, Vol. 28A, 1997, pp. 237-243.
5. Barlow, C.Y. and Hansen, N., “Dislocation Configurations in Metal-Matrix Composites Correlated with Numerical Predictions”, *Acta Metall. Mater.*, Vol. 43, No. 10, 1995, pp. 3633-3648.
6. Wilkinson, A.J. and Dingley, D.J., “The Distribution of Plastic Deformation in a Metal Matrix Composite Caused by Straining Transverse to the Fibre Direction”, *Acta Metall. Mater.*, Vol. 40, No. 12, 1992, pp. 3357-3368.
7. Allais, L., Bornert, M., Bretheau, T. and Caldemaison, D., “Experimental Characterization of the Local Strain Field in a Heterogeneous Elastoplastic Material”, *Acta Metall. Mater.*, Vol. 42, No. 11, 1994, pp. 3865-3880.
8. Crostack, H.-A. and Fischer, G., *Beitrage zur eiektronenmikroskopischen Direktabbildung und Analyse von Oberflachen (BEDO) Vol.29*, in press, (1996).
9. Liu Y.L. and Fischer, G., “In-Situ Measurement of Local Strain in a Metal Matrix Composite by the Object Grating Technique”, *Scripta Mater.*, Vol. 36, No. 10, 1997, pp. 1187-1194.